

ENHANCEMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF HISTORY IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE AND ITS CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS

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After we gained independence, as in all fields, the science of history faced an urgent problem. The reason is that 130 years of colonialism and the system of the Soviets forced us to set particular limits in writing history. If we observe the process of the emergence of modern historical science from the territory of our country, it corresponds to the beginning of the 20th century. It was during this period that professor P. Soliev, A. Fitrat etc. came out. But we can explain that their number is a minority, the number of research subjects is extremely small, and the number of universities, which are the basis for the process of personnel training, is also limited.

In this regard, it is appropriate to cite the period after 1941 of the Second World War, which entered Soviet historiography under the name of the "Great Patriotic War", as an event that caused changes. By this time, one of the great historians of our country, A.Yu. Yakubovsky and K.V. Together with teaching local students, the Trevers made a certain contribution to the creation of scientific historical works in our country [1]. The most important innovation of this period was the establishment of the Institute of History in the system of the Academy of Sciences in 1945 [2].

The establishment of the Institute of Oriental Studies, which today is considered another major scientific research institute in the Academy system, also took place during this period: in 1943, it was founded on the basis of the Oriental Department of the State Library of Uzbekistan (now the State Library named after Alisher Navoi) and until 1950 was called the Institute for the Study of Oriental Manuscripts. In 1950, it was named the Institute of Oriental Studies, taking into account the scope of scientific fields conducted at the Institute. At present, about 26,000 volumes of manuscripts are stored in the treasury of manuscripts.

Most of them contain several works. The total number of printed and published books is about 40,000 volumes. They are of great importance in studying the history of Central Asia, as well as Eastern countries - Arab countries, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Turkey, China, Iran, and India. About 10,000 historical documents are also stored in the manuscript treasury of the Institute [3: 11].

In recent years, the number of research institutions and universities training specialists in the field has increased.

If we look at the research in the field of history in the early years of independence, we can see that the historiography and the methodological approach were dominated by the Marxist view. By 1998, as a result of a meeting with the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov and a group of historians, the question of rewriting history in the "national spirit" was raised, and we are not mistaken in saying that this reality will serve as a certain methodological basis for the next period. Here are the priorities for historians:

- The history of the origin of the Uzbek people;
- History of Uzbek statehood;
- Issues such as researching our material and spiritual heritage can be pointed out.

The Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Institute of Oriental Studies and the Institute of Archeology were designated as the main scientific organizations in the implementation of these tasks, as well as Tashkent State University (at the moment, the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek) [4: 145].

Most of the works carried out in the following years were carried out based on this criterion.

If we look at the period after 2016 based on a separate prism, the fourth priority of the direction "Development of the social sphere" of the Action Strategy on the five priority directions of Uzbekistan's development in 2017-2021, adopted on February 7, 2017, is dedicated to "Development of the education sphere". The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, emphasized his noble thoughts that "Ensuring our peaceful life depends on the education and upbringing of our youth, worldview and preservation of our ancient traditions..." [5]. On December 30, 2016, our president Sh. Mirziyoev's meeting with the leading scientific representatives of our country also focused on this field [6]. On June 30, 2017, the Presidential Decree "On the establishment of the public council for the study of the latest history of Uzbekistan under the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was signed [7]. The decision of the President of May 24, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources" [8] and the adoption of other legal documents related to several other fields serve as a legal basis for the development of historiography.

However, some scientists have expressed their opinions about the work that should be done in this regard, including PhD. B. Alimzhanov, assessing the state of historical science in today's Uzbekistan, states that becoming an equal

member of world historiography is the task facing the historian of Uzbekistan as the main problem. At the same time, he evaluates the history of the past period as follows: "Our historiography shows that for the last 75 years, historians have become the executors of the government's "task" and are active participants in "political games". Science should not be put aside and political "interests" should come first. History is not part of politics, but politics is part of history. The historian of Uzbekistan, who has not forgotten this fact, will surely write scientific history based on sources and relying on the achievements of world history" [1]. Another famous historian Sh. Kamoliddin emphasizes that the number of non-scientific views on the current state of the history of Uzbekistan has increased, the amount of non-scientific works that do not correspond to the real truth has increased due to the lack of attention to the field by the state, and the number of personnel who can respond to some of the biased works of Western scientists has decreased. [9: 58-68].

On February 17, 2021, on the portal for the discussion of normative legal documents, President Shavkat Mirziyoev, on January 19, 2021, the meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment of the Republic held in the video selector style, in order to ensure the implementation of paragraph 27 of statement 3, the Cabinet of Ministers "Development of the science of history in Uzbekistan in 2021-2030 concept" project was announced. During the discussion of this issue academician A. Sagdullaev, PhD prof., B. Babadjanov, PhD. B. Alimdjanov, PhD. Tulkin Bobomatov and others expressed their attitude towards the project and recommended its revision [10]. As the main reason for this, they connected the attempt of the Institute of History as a leading organization to establish a monopoly in the field, the limitation of the scope of research work, the issue of integration with world historiography not being fully disclosed, and several other reasons. Today, this project is considered to be in the process of reformation, and if it is adopted, it will serve as the main regulatory legal document in the field for the next ten years.

Also, if we consider the work carried out in the field in recent years on the example of institutes, each institute contributes to the development of the field to a certain extent, in particular, the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni, during the years of independence, catalogues of rare works in the manuscript fund of more than 40 institutes were formed, in August of this year the main fund catalogue was digitized and made available through an electronic platform [11]. This certainly creates a foundation for the lifelong existence of rare manuscripts that reflect the history, culture, and religion of our

country and are included in the UNESCO list. At the same time, the funds for manuscripts in our country are being enriched, and new scientifically important sources are being put into circulation after the constant archeographic expeditions carried out by the working group of the institute [8].

If we look at the activity of the Institute of History, the institute is divided into departments based on the principle of periodicity and more than 80 monographs have been published in the last decade (2011-2021). It is the organization with the largest quota in the Republic in terms of the number of young scientists (doctoral students, basic doctoral students, intern-researchers). The Institute of Axreology and the National Centers of Archeology have also carried out important works in their fields, and it should be noted that two types of research of representatives of the field have taken place in the ranking of important discoveries made in recent years (on the kun. uz site) [12]. At the same time, they showed enthusiasm in forming the list of immovable property objects of material cultural heritage.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that since the independence of Uzbekistan, more than 20 NHHs related to the sector have been adopted. In the early period, scientific research was developed in a scattered subject matter and not separated from the idea of Marxism, but starting from 1998, a proposal was made to re-create the field, and in this regard, the creation of national history was set as a priority task.

In the period after 2016, as a result of the revision of scientific research works following foreign standards, favourable conditions for researchers have been created. Their material support was equal to that of the CIS countries. The diversity of opinions is still observed today, which we can consider in the framework of the discussion of the project "Concept for the development of the science of history in Uzbekistan in 2021-2030".

We believe that the biggest shortcomings in the field are that the training of personnel in the auxiliary fields of history in higher education institutions is not up to the level of demand, the implementation of integration projects with world history issues, in particular, the countries of Central Asia, is not sufficient, and the researches related to the field are not analyzed based on "ilmmetric" studies.

References:

- 1.https://www.uzanalytics.com.translate.google/tarix/3686/?_x_tr_sl=uz&_x_tr_tl=ru&_x_tr_hl=ru&_x_tr_pto=sc
- 2.<https://www.academy.uz/uz/page/biz-haqimizda>

3. Abduhalimov B. Treasury of Manuscripts. // Treasury of Eastern Manuscripts. Institute of Oriental Studies is named after Abu Rayhan Beruni, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2012.
4. Karimov I. Works. Volume VII. Tashkent. 1999.
5. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people.-T: "Uzbekistan". 2017. 467- p.
6. Scientific-methodological treatise on the study of the State program on the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of communication with the people and human interests" in 2017-2021.-T. : "Spirituality". 2017. - 99 p.
7. On the establishment of the public council for the study of the latest history of Uzbekistan under the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. //"Marifat" newspaper, July 1, 2017, No. 52 (9013)
8. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2995. On measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources. // <https://lex.uz/docs/-3211987>
9. Kamoliddin Sh.S. Actual problems of the historiography of the history of Central Asia. 2nd edition. TDSHI. Tashkent. 2019.
10. <https://regulation.gov.uz/uz/d/31751>
11. Electronic catalogue of manuscripts of the Main Fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies. // <http://scam.beruni.uz/scam/>
12. <https://kun.uz/news/2022/02/17/yangi-yulduzdan-kofirkalagacha-uzbek-olimlarin-songgi-ten-yillikdagi-eng-muhim-10-kashfiyot-va-hitronari>